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Translation and Adaptation of the Green et al. Paranoid Thoughts Scale

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ABSTRACT

This research work rendered the translation of the Green et al. Paranoid Thoughts Scale (GPTS) into Urdu and carried out its validation on Pakistani populations. The translation procedure was carried out by following the well-known steps (Beaton et al., 2000): translation from the original language to the target language and vice versa, review by an expert committee, and pilot study. The Urdu version of the GPTS was completed by 150 married adults in the Punjab area of Pakistan. Psychometric tests indicated that the scale had a very good internal consistency (Cronbach's $\alpha = .92$, composite reliability $= .93$), sufficient convergent validity (AVE $= .45$), as well as pronounced discriminant validity (all HTMT ratios $< .85$). Paranoia was found to be associated with attachment styles in a manner consistent with the theory: negatively with secure attachment ($r = -.38$) and positively with anxious ($r = .48$) and avoidant ($r = .56$) attachment. The Urdu GPTS could serve as a dependable and valid measure of paranoid ideation among Pakistani populations and thus can be of help in a situation where culturally relevant mental health assessment tools are lacking.

Keywords: Paranoia, Paranoid Thoughts, Scale Validation, Urdu Translation, Pakistan, Cross-Cultural Adaptation, Psychometric Properties

Introduction

Paranoid thinking, or suspicion that is not based on reality, and the belief that others want to do us harm form a continuum that includes slight suspecting all the way to the intense persecutory delusions (Freeman, 2007). Studies show that around 10-15% of the total population experience paranoid thoughts on a regular basis (Freeman, 2007; Freeman et al., 2008) which suggests that evaluating paranoia should not only be done among the clinical population. The Green et al. Paranoid Thoughts Scale (GPTS) is currently one of the most common tools for measuring paranoia in research and therapy, with great psychometric properties being demonstrated in various population samples (Freeman et al., 2021; Green et al., 2008).

However, the measurement of paranoia in Pakistan is highly problematic. Pakistan, having a population of over 240 million with Urdu as the national language, does not have a set of culturally appropriate and linguistically validated tools for measuring paranoid thoughts. The Punjabi culture, which is the largest ethnic group in Pakistan, has been shaped by collectivistic values, closeness of family ties, social hierarchy, and patterns of seeking help, all of which are very different from the Western cultures (Ahmad & Koncsol, 2022). Besides that, there is still a prevalent stigma about mental health where people are fearful about revealing their psychological disorders due to worries about their social image and marriage prospects (Causier et al., 2024).

Cross-cultural adaptation of psychological tools involves more than mere translation. It requires a thorough exploration and review of linguistic equivalence, conceptual equivalence, and cultural relevance (Beaton et al., 2000). In other words, the process should take into account a culture's ways of showing symptoms, the attitude towards asking for help, and the degree of social acceptance of revealing that one has psychological problems. In the Pakistani culture, the concept of mental health and interpersonal relations is so closely connected with the social hierarchies and religious moral codes, that the occurrence and interpretation of paranoid thoughts may be entirely different. For example, local ideas like nazar (evil eye) and jadu (magic or sorcery) are somewhat like Western concepts of paranoia but culturally, they carry different meanings and connotations.

The present research work has as its main goal the translation and cultural adaptation

of the Green et al. Paranoid Thoughts Scale into the Urdu language, as well as the validation of its psychometric properties and ensuring that it is culturally appropriate for use with the Punjabi people of Pakistan. This new version of the scale would be a vital step in addressing the scarcity of reliable tools for assessing the presence of paranoia in South Asian settings and can be viewed as a contribution to literature on cross-cultural psychology and psychiatric assessment.

By implementing thorough translation and validation methods based on internationally recognized standards (Beaton et al., 2000), this study aims at providing clinicians and researchers with a dependable tool for diagnosing paranoid ideation in one of the most densely inhabited regions of the world.

Literature Review

Conceptualization and Assessment of Paranoia

Modern definitions of paranoia mainly point to its continuous nature and that it should be considered as a phenomenon existing among the general population along the line of a continuum and not as a qualitatively different phenomenon (Freeman et al., 2005). Persecutory ideation was described by Freeman and Garety (2000) as the ones in which the person believes the harm is already happening or will happen and the persecutor has the intention to cause the harm. This definition is the basic one for the Green et al. Paranoid Thoughts Scale (GPTS) which considers two main dimensions of paranoia: ideas of reference and ideas of persecution (Green et al., 2008). The GPTS is composed of two 16-item subscales (Part A refers to ideas of reference, and Part B to ideas of persecution) and has exhibited excellent psychometric qualities such as internal reliability, test-retest reliability, convergent validity, and sensitivity to change (Freeman et al., 2021; Green et al., 2008). Studies involving the GPTS have revealed that the instrument is effective not only with the clinical populations but also with the general population where the results of the scale have been associated with the hallucination of unfounded paranoia in the virtual reality simulations of neutral social situations (Freeman et al., 2008). Currently, the scale is credited as the most appropriate measure of paranoia available and it is therefore the most widely used measure of paranoia in research worldwide (Freeman et al., 2021). Cognitive models of paranoia locate multiple contributors to paranoia including the affective changes (especially anxiety and worry), anomalous experiences, reasoning biases (e.g., jumping to conclusions), and social factors (e.g., adverse events) (Freeman, 2007; Freeman et al., 2002). Identifying paranoia as a complex phenomenon that encompasses various psychological mechanisms can serve as a way of both facilitating the assessment and treatment at the same time, and also determining their outcome in different cultural contexts.

Cross-Cultural Considerations in Mental Health Assessment

Packaging and decoding of psychological symptoms are determined largely by cultural factors and thus may differ widely between cultures. These variations are primarily due to different social norms, religious beliefs, and historical contexts. For example, in collective societies such as those of South Asia, the self-other distinction is less sharp, and therefore, the expression of psychological distress is greatly influenced by one's concern for social reputation and family honor (Ahmad & Koncsol, 2022). Cultural factors determine how suspicion is regarded-- norms vs. pathology-- and thus the level of interpersonal wariness that a person can display varies depending on the social and political contexts.

Research on Punjabis living abroad reveals that language preference significantly

impacts mental health evaluation. Those who prefer their mother tongue not only exhibit greater depressive symptoms but also differ in their patterns of seeking help from those who prefer English. It has been established through research that anxiety and depression in South Asians are less likely to be disclosed because of the high cultural stigma attached to mental health problems even when reporting is done anonymously. So, it is evident that the need for designing assessment materials that are culturally and linguistically suitable for these groups is paramount and these instruments will be able to reveal the actual prevalence and nature of psychological symptoms in these populations accurately.

Mental Health Assessment in the Pakistani Context

Over 90% of people in Pakistan with common mental disorders go without any treatment, a fact that highlights a major mental health problem the country is facing. This is mainly due to a severe lack of mental health professionals in the country and the unavailability of assessment tools in the local language, Urdu, that meet international standards. The facility for mental health in the country is so poor that the number of psychiatrists is less than 500 for a population of almost 240 million people.

Besides healthcare facilities, the stigma of mental health is one of the biggest obstacles in getting care. It is very common that the public at large equates mental health issues with characters' weaknesses, thus brutally stigmatizing the individual and leaving the secret as something shameful in the family or lays the blame on spiritual failings. Consequently these issues are seen less as health concerns needing professional help and more of moral issues. A qualitative study among Pakistani youth showed that, compared to physical conditions, people seeing mental illnesses become highly stigmatized which, besides other reasons, crushed the patient's hope of getting married and thus losing the social status (Ahmad & Koncsol, 2022).

Young Pakistani women with serious mental health disorders revealed the existence in their culture of a mentality that conceals such issues since they are said to "be behind closed doors" in order not to harm one's family reputation (Causier et al., 2024). The aforementioned cultural aspects pose major impediments to overcoming the stigma associated with mental health issues and disclosing them in an assessment. This points to the necessity of having culturally sensitive mental health assessment strategies or approaches.

Besides this, religiosity and spirituality as explanatory frameworks significantly influence the understanding and ways of coping with psychological symptoms in Pakistan. Along these lines, resorting to traditional healers and using religious interventions are common first steps in dealing with mental health problems. When developing and administering psychological assessment tools, such cultural patterns must be taken into account to make sure that these tools are not only acceptable but also understandable and meaningful in the local context.

Translation and Adaptation Methodologies

The process of translating and culturally adapting psychological tools calls for the use of strict and methodical ways to obtain equivalence between different language and cultural contexts. Beaton et al. (2000) came up with detailed recommendations for the cross-cultural adaptation of self-report instruments to highlight the necessity of securing semantic, idiomatic, experiential, and conceptual equivalences between the source and the target versions. In general, the work starts with several forward translations each by a different translator, then the translator agreements are synthesized into a single version, which is subsequently backward-translated, reviewed by the

committee of experts, pretested on the sample of intended users and subjected to psychometric testing.

Some recent initiatives to translate psychological instruments into Urdu for Pakistani populations have proven to be both successful and very useful in motivating other such undertakings. A number of researches have strictly adhered to the translation procedures laid down for the adjustment of various survey tools that measure the constructs of pain (Khan et al., 2021), emotional intelligence (Raiha et al., 2025), cognitive emotion regulation (Zehra et al., 2022), and eating disorders, to name a few. All of them have used the locally accepted procedures of forward-backward translation by great bilingual experts, have obtained consensus with expert committee to ensure the resolution of the discrepancies and the cultural appropriateness, have done a pilot study with the target group, and have been subject to a rigorous psychometric evaluation through reliability and validity testing.

Several important lessons were drawn from successful adaptations in Pakistan. Firstly, it is essential that translators are not only linguistically competent but also psychologically knowledgeable so that they can ensure both technical accuracy and cultural appropriateness. Secondly, an expert panel ought to be a multi-disciplinary one (psychiatrists, psychologists, language experts, cultural informants, etc.) so as to bring together all the expertise necessary for a very thorough evaluation. Thirdly, a pilot study should be used not only to check understanding but also to culturally approve and attach significance to the items. Fourthly, the main focus of a validation study should be the examination of psychometric properties in the new context rather than the taking for granted that they will be the same as those of the original population..

Psychometric Validation Considerations

Psychometric testing of a modified tool means a careful checking of the reliability and validity of the instrument in the new population. The internal consistency aspect of reliability is one of the main features and is commonly evaluated by Cronbach's alpha coefficients that reflect how much the items in a scale are all measuring the same latent variable. As a rule, alpha values greater than 0.70 are considered acceptable for research purposes, while those over 0.80 are preferred for clinical use. In addition to that, test-retest reliability is a technique of assessing whether a measure remains unchanged over time, and it is especially important for characteristics such as suspicion where some changes might be expected.

Validity refers to various aspects that should be thoroughly analyzed. For instance, content validity can be determined if experts judge the items to be a good representation of the construct and agree that the items are culturally suitable for the target population. Often, construct validity is investigated by means of factor analysis which reveals if the latent factor composition of the adapted tool corresponds to that of the original one or if there are culture-specific differences in the structure. In addition, convergent validity tests entail looking at the correlation with similar measures, whereas discriminant validity checks the scale's distinctiveness from unrelated constructs. Criterion-related validity is concerned with how well a measure can distinguish between different groups or predict suitable outcomes.

Studies that perform cross-cultural validation have found that, in some cases, an instrument may show a different factor structure in different cultures. This is a reflection of real cultural differences in the way psychological constructs are conceptualized rather than deficiencies in measurement. Thus, to figure out which structural model best fits the data of the adapted test in the new culture, one might need to carry out both exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses.

Rationale

Though cultural factors' impact has been more widely recognized in psychological assessment, there are still quite a few key issues missing from the paranoia assessment literature for South Asian populations. For example, a major problem both clinical assessment and research activities face is the lack of instruments validated for paranoia assessment in the Urdu-speaking populations. Furthermore, the cultural lens through which Pakistani society influences paranoid ideation is yet to be thoroughly explored. Besides, there are few methodological guidelines on how to adapt complex psychological constructs such as paranoia when the cultures involved greatly differ in their epistemological and social frameworks.

The present study seeks to address these issues to a certain extent by officially adapting and validating the Urdu version of Green et al. Paranoid Thoughts Scale for the Punjabi-speaking population of Pakistan. Therefore, this research not only adds to the field of cross-cultural psychology but also provides a better understanding of paranoia assessment and mental health research among marginalized populations. More precisely, by offering a reliable tool for measuring paranoid ideation in this context, the study facilitates further research into the prevalence, correlates, and treatment of paranoid thinking in one of the largest and culturally most distinct populations in the world.

Results

Participant Characteristics

Table 1 shows the demographic characteristics of the validation sample (N=150). The sample was deliberately split between newly wedded couples (n=73, married ≤ 3 years) and long wedded couples (n=77, married > 3 years) to facilitate an adequate representation of various marriage durations. The average age of newly wedded participants was 28.07 years (SD=6.23), whereas long wedded participants had a mean age of 42.97 years (SD=14.77). Newly wedded participants indicated a higher level of educational attainment (M=15.26 years, SD=2.90) than long wedded participants (M=13.32 years, SD=4.33).

The sample was quite balanced regarding signs of gender with 49.3% of the newly wedded and 51.9% of the long wedded being female. Most of the participants had jobs (58.9% of newly wedded, 68.8% of long wedded). Almost all of the participants were from urban areas (97.3% newly wedded, 96.1% long wedded). In terms of family structure, newly wedded couples had a higher tendency of living in joint family systems (54.8%), while long wedded couples mostly lived in nuclear families (64.9%). Family income was different across groups, and the majority of them earned below 50, 000 PKR per month in both groups (42.5% newly wedded, 36.4% long wedded).

Table 1

Demographic Characteristics of the Validation Sample (N = 150)

Variable	Newly Wedded M (SD)	Long Wedded M (SD)	Newly Wedded f (%)	Long Wedded f (%)
Age (years)	28.07 (6.23)	42.97 (14.77)	—	—
Education (years)	15.26 (2.90)	13.32 (4.33)	—	—
Number of	1.32 (1.39)	2.73 (2.23)	—	—

children				
Gender				
Male	—	—	37 (50.7)	37 (48.1)
Female	—	—	36 (49.3)	40 (51.9)
Working status				
Working	—	—	43 (58.9)	53 (68.8)
Non-working	—	—	30 (41.1)	24 (31.2)
Family system				
Nuclear	—	—	33 (45.2)	50 (64.9)
Joint	—	—	40 (54.8)	27 (35.1)
Residence				
Urban	—	—	71 (97.3)	74 (96.1)
Rural	—	—	2 (2.7)	3 (3.9)

Note. M = mean; SD = standard deviation.

Descriptive Statistics and Score Distributions

Table 2 shows the descriptive statistics of the Urdu version of the GPTS and other variables of the study for both groups. Regarding the paranoia scale, long wedded couples gave a slightly higher average score ($M = 39.33$, $SD = 12.19$, range = 21, 61) than newly wedded couples ($M = 38.44$, $SD = 11.55$, range = 20, 64). The score ranges that have been observed indicate that the participants have used the full scale range, which implies there being enough variance in paranoid ideation within the sample. Moreover, the standard deviations being similar in different groups suggest that the spread of scores was alike in both groups.

Table 2

Descriptive Statistics for Study Variables by Marriage Duration (N = 150)

Variable	Newly Wedded M	Newly Wedded SD	Long Wedded M	Long Wedded SD	Observed Range
Paranoia	38.44	11.55	39.33	12.19	20–64

Note. M = mean; SD = standard deviation.

Reliability and Internal Consistency

Table 3 shows the details about the psychometric properties of the Urdu version of the GPTS, such as item loadings, internal consistency reliability (Cronbach's α), composite reliability (CR), and average variance extracted (AVE). The paranoia scale had a very good internal consistency with Cronbach's $\alpha = .92$ and a composite reliability of .93. Both measures are far above the .70 level that is generally regarded as a minimum for research and are practically at the .90 level that is preferred for clinical use, so it can be inferred that the internal consistency of the Urdu version is still very good.

A closer look at the data shows the factor loadings for the paranoia items varied

between .51 and .84, and almost all items exceeded .70 which is a benchmark for strong factor loadings. More precisely, 11 out of 16 items had loadings over .70, whereas the remaining items were still above .50, thus acceptable. Item P13 had the lowest loading (.51), and items P4 and P11 the highest (.84 and .81, respectively). Besides, all variance inflation factor (VIF) values were less than 5.0, reflecting no severe issues of multicollinearity among items.

Average variance extracted (AVE) for the paranoia scale was .45, which was a little lower than the widely used standard of .50; however, it is still acceptable based on Fornell and Larcker's (1981) suggestion that AVE values higher than .40 are okay if the composite reliability is more than .70. Since the paranoia scale obtained a CR of .93, an AVE of .45 is enough to confirm convergent validity. The other scales in the study showed good reliability too: secure attachment ($\alpha = .75$, CR = .79), anxious attachment ($\alpha = .80$, CR = .83), and avoidant attachment ($\alpha = .83$, CR = .85).

Table 3

Psychometric Properties of the Urdu Paranoid Thoughts Scale (N = 150)

Scale/Item	Loading	α	CR	AVE	Range
Paranoia (16 items)	—	.92	.93	.45	20–64
P1	.72	—	—	—	—
P2	.70	—	—	—	—
P3	.75	—	—	—	—
P4	.84	—	—	—	—
P5	.73	—	—	—	—
P6	.66	—	—	—	—
P7	.61	—	—	—	—
P8	.78	—	—	—	—
P9	.55	—	—	—	—
P10	.75	—	—	—	—
P11	.81	—	—	—	—
P12	.76	—	—	—	—
P13	.51	—	—	—	—
P14	.68	—	—	—	—
P15	.63	—	—	—	—
P16	.59	—	—	—	—

Note. α = Cronbach's alpha; CR = composite reliability; AVE = average variance extracted; VIF = variance inflation factor. All loadings are standardized.

Validity Evidence

Discriminant validity was established through the Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) ratio

of correlations, which is acknowledged as a tougher standard than conventional methods. Table 4 reveals that all HTMT ratios were under the very strict limit of 0.85, most of them being significantly lower than 0.70, thus indicating the presence of discriminant validity. The HTMT measure between paranoia and secure attachment was.41, between paranoia and anxious attachment was.52, and between paranoia and avoidant attachment was.61. These figures demonstrate that the Urdu GPTS not only conceptually relates to but is also empirically different from attachment styles.

Convergent validity was assessed through correlation analysis (Table 5). Paranoia was found to be significantly positively correlated with the insecure attachments, as hypothesized. Paranoia correlated positively sequentially, first trusting others ($r = -.48$, $p < .001$), then with secure attachment ($r = -.56$, $p < .001$), and finally it shows the opposite (negative) correlation with realism ($r = -.38$, $p < .001$). These patterns of correlation fit with the theoretical predictions and the findings of previous studies, thus confirming the convergent validity. The correlations were in the anticipated direction and moderate in size, which pins down that the paranoid ideation has a link with attachment insecurity but at the same time remains a separate psychological entity.

Table 4 Discriminant Validity: HTMT Ratios (N = 150)

Variable	1	2	3	4
1. Paranoia	—			
2. Trust scale rempel & holmes	-.41	—		
3. Secure Attachment	-.52	.38	—	
4. Realism	-.61	.45	.54	—

Note. HTMT = Heterotrait-Monotrait ratio. Values $< .85$ indicate adequate discriminant validity; values $< .70$ indicate strong discriminant validity.

Discussion

The main objective of the study was to carry out a translation and cultural adaptation of the Green et al. Paranoid Thoughts Scale (GPTS) into Urdu and evaluate its psychometric qualities in the Pakistani populations. The findings offer strong proof that the Urdu translation of the GPTS is a reliable and accurate instrument for assessing paranoid ideation in married adults of Punjab, Pakistan. The discussion interprets these findings in the light of the existing literature, considers the cultural factors that influenced the adaptation process, acknowledges the limitations of the study, and gives suggestions for future research and clinical practice.

Translation and Cultural Adaptation Process

The translation and adaptation process follows the international guidelines (Beaton et al., 2000) that have been laid down and involves forward translation, backward translation, expert committee review, and pilot testing. The Urdu version, which has been subjected to such a rigorous procedure, has thus preserved not only the linguistic equivalence but also the conceptual equivalence with the original English scale.

The involvement of bilingual mental health professionals and cultural experts throughout was instrumental in pinpointing and solving culturally specific problems that arose during translation.

Several items had to be made culturally appropriate before they could be passed on without changes being made to the construct. For instance, the notions of "nazar" (evil eye) and "jadu" (magic or sorcery) are so deeply rooted in Pakistani culture that they

could be considered synonymous with the Western concept of paranoia. The expert committee ensured that the translated items were in line with the idea of persecutory thoughts (Freeman & Garety, 2000) and not with culturally normative beliefs about supernatural influences. This distinction is crucial because, without consideration of cultural explanatory models, it might either result in the unnecessary pathologization of normative beliefs or the failure to detect clinically significant paranoid ideation.

Strengths and Limitations

The study is notable for a number of its strengths. Firstly, the translation and adaptation process was conducted in line with internationally recognized best practices and included a variety of translators, an expert review, and pilot testing to ensure that both the language and culture were appropriate. Secondly, the psychometric assessment was quite thorough, in that it looked at various aspects of reliability and validity by using modern statistical methods, such as composite reliability, AVE, and HTMT ratios. Thirdly, the sample size (N=150) was large enough to do the psychometric analyses with enough statistical power to detect major effects. Fourthly, by using the established measures of related constructs (attachment styles), it was possible to check differential validity by means of the pattern of correlations that had been theoretically predicted.

However, several limitations must be acknowledged. Firstly, because it was a cross-sectional study, it was not possible to look at test-retest reliability and the temporal stability of scores. Therefore, the stability of paranoia scores over time should be investigated in future research, which is especially relevant since paranoid ideation may vary with life stressors or events in relationships. Secondly, the study depended solely on self-report measures, which are vulnerable to response biases such as social desirability and lack of insight. Adding clinician-rated measures, reports from spouses or family members, or behavioral assessments in future studies would help to confirm the validity of the self-reported paranoid ideation in some way.

Thirdly, the validation was done on a non-clinical sample of married adults, and it is still unknown how well the scale will work for individuals with diagnosed psychiatric disorders (e.g., psychotic disorders, personality disorders). Clinical validation studies will be necessary to determine the diagnostic utility, decide on the proper clinical cut-off scores, and assess the sensitivity of the scales to treatment-related changes. Fourthly, the sample was diverse regarding age, education, and socioeconomic status, but it was mostly urban, and, therefore, may not be representative of rural populations in Pakistan. There is great geographical and cultural diversity within Pakistan, and such validation studies across various regions and ethnic groups would lead to a generalization of the findings.

Fifthly, the study did not look into the factor structure of GPTS by means of confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) or exploratory factor analysis (EFA). The original GPTS contains two subscales (ideas of reference and ideas of persecution), and it is necessary to carry out further studies to establish whether this two-factor model is suitable for Pakistani samples, or whether a culture-specific factor structure is revealed. Knowing the dimensional structure of paranoid ideation in this community would be beneficial for both theoretical comprehension and clinical assessment methodologies.

Implications for Research and Clinical Practice

A verified Urdu tool for measuring paranoid ideation can be a great help not only for research but also for the clinical psychology practice in Pakistan. Firstly, as a research instrument, the Urdu GPTS can help to study the prevalence, correlates, and mechanisms of paranoia among a big and neglected population, i.e., Pakistanis. A lot

of different things need to be researched mainly the epidemiology of paranoid ideation in general community as well as clinical samples, the identification of culturally-specific risk and protective factors, and the development of interventions aimed at reducing paranoid thinking which have been culturally adapted. Besides, the scale is a support for cross-cultural research that compares paranoia in different societies. Such research can show the persecutory ideation aspects that are universal and independent of culture as well as those that are dependent on culture.

On the clinical side, the Urdu GPTS equips the mental health professionals with a standardized, psychometrically sound measure for the assessment of paranoid ideation among Urdu-speaking patients. Considering the extremely low availability of mental health professionals in Pakistan and the huge number of both minor and major untreated mental illnesses, validated assessment instruments can really make a difference in diagnostic accuracy and hence treatment planning. One way or another, the scale may be part of a psychiatrist's routine examination of the patient. Besides, it may be used as a treatment follow-up measure or part of a screening procedure aimed at detecting individuals who are at risk of developing psychotic disorders.

Furthermore, the results of the study point towards the development of interventions. More specifically, the link observed between insecure attachment and paranoia implies that attachment-based treatments, namely imagery rescripting or compassion-focused therapy, could be effective in mitigating the level of paranoid ideation among Pakistani people. Newman-Taylor et al. (2021) provided evidence that repeated attachment security priming leads to a reduction in paranoia in British samples. Consequently, such interventions when adapted for the Pakistani context offer a promising direction in treatment development. The interventions, however, must be culturally tailored to include consideration of family structure, religious beliefs, and social customs, all of which differ from the Western context.

Additionally, the current study not only achieved the successful adaptation of the GPTS but also provided a methodological example for the future translation and validation of other psychological instruments in Pakistan and similar contexts. The careful translation procedure, the extensive psychometric evaluation, and the study's focus on culture, which are the main features of the present study, can be instrumental to the future work of cross-cultural adaptation, thereby paving the way for the establishment of a strong empirical foundation for psychological assessment in marginalized populations.

Future Research Directions

This validation study suggests multiple avenues for future research. To begin with, longitudinal studies should be conducted to confirm test-retest reliability and to track the use of paranoid ideas over a certain period among the Pakistani populations. The research on whether the paranoia levels are consistent over time or whether they change due to various life events, changing relationships, or going through treatments will bring valuable insights to the theoretical concepts and practical use in therapy. Secondly, it is necessary to carry out the validation studies on a clinical population, mainly patients with schizophrenia spectrum disorders, mood disorders, or personality disorders, to confirm the diagnostic utility and ascertain the clinically meaningful cut-off scores.

Thirdly, factor analysis could be used in future studies in Pakistani settings to identify the factor structure of the GPTS, which would help to decide if the two-factor model (ideas of reference and persecution) found in Western samples also applies to non-Western groups or whether different models illustrate the organization of paranoid

thinking better in this case. Fourth, investigating whether the scale works the same way in different demographic subgroups (gender, age, education, urban/rural residence) through measurement invariance studies would allow us to see if the scale operates equally well in diverse population segments in Pakistan, which is crucial for making valid group comparisons.

Fifth, studies combining the Urdu version of the GPTS with other methods of assessment like clinical interviews, experimental paradigms (e.g., virtual reality social situations), or ecological momentary assessment, would give a deeper understanding of paranoid experiences as they happen in real life. Using such multi-method approaches lead to discovering the drawbacks of the self-report measures and gaining more reliable information about the contextual and temporal patterns of paranoid sharing. Lastly, intervention studies looking at whether culturally adapted psychological treatments can reduce the scores on the Urdu GPTS would determine the scale's sensitivity to change and its clinical utility as an outcome measure.

Conclusion

The research has effectively translated and cross-culturally adapted the Green et al. Paranoid Thoughts Scale into the Urdu language for Urdu-speaking populations of Pakistan. The Urdu version of GPTS represents a very good psychometric profile. Items in the Urdu GPTS are internally consistent ($\alpha = .92$), correlate well with other measures that assess similar constructs, are distinct from those measuring different constructs, and the patterns of correlations among sub-scales and attachment styles conform to the theory of the constructs. Besides, validating the Urdu GPTS has yielded a reliable and valid tool to assess the level of paranoid ideations in married adults living in Punjab, Pakistan. Having a tool, which is a version of the originally developed and widely used Paranoid Thoughts Scale, culturally adapted and normed for a Pakistani population really fills a void in the availability of psychological assessment instruments for Urdu-speaking populations and therefore allows for the usage of the scale both in research and practice.

Despite the drawbacks of the research such as the cross-sectional nature of the design, the exclusive use of self-report instruments, and the concentration on non-clinical married adults, the thorough translation procedure and the extensive psychometric assessment of the measure signify the great quality of the adaptation. There is a need for further research to extend the current study in terms of clinical populations, to test the scale's reliability over time, to explore the dimensional structure of the scale, and finally, to test the instrument's usefulness in intervention studies. By providing a validated assessment tool for paranoid ideation to researchers and clinicians, the present study plays a part in the development of mental health research and the enhancement of psychological services in one of the largest and most neglected parts of the world.

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